

PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT AND STRUCTURE OF EDUCATION OF STUDENTS THROUGH SPORTS

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Annotation: In this article, the theoretical-methodological foundations of the formation of national identity in students through sports, the role of national traditional values of holidays, ceremonies, customs and events as a source of national education are of particular importance. playing was explained.

Key words and phrases: sports, folk traditional values, intercultural relations, practical skills, continuous education, individual qualities, economic development, educational standards, education and training, scientific-methodical, subjective innovation in students.

Education of students through sports, harmonizing their physical and voluntary qualities, is a pedagogical process aimed at their mental and physical growth, and is considered one of the important components of the social education system. After all, "the low level of organization of work on creating conditions for the widespread involvement of young people in physical education and mass sports, for ensuring the harmonious spiritual and physical development of the growing generation, as a result - physical insufficient coverage of people who want to engage in education and mass sports" [1] justifies the need to improve the system of forming a culture of physical and healthy lifestyle in students.

In this paragraph, the pedagogical and psychological features of educating students through sports are studied. Also, the principles of the pedagogical process aimed at forming physical culture in students were analyzed.

Strengthening the health of our people is one of the main tasks of physical culture. In front of physical education, more physical culture and sports should be integrated into the life of our people; in raising young people in the spirit of independence, there are great tasks such as improving people's health and preparing them for the defense of the Motherland, using all different forms of social education and sports, including folk traditions. The national games of our people are one of the important physical and sports tools widely used for this purpose. Therefore, the need to increase attention to the national games of the people is even more obvious.

People's national games play an important role in the development of children's physical qualities. Because games increase students' interests, give them pleasure, and ensure faster recovery of work skills. Thanks to the games, children forget about fatigue and try to do the exercises carefully.

All national folk games have a holistic effect on children's bodies. That is why games should be considered as having a general physical effect. The one and only goal of all areas and stages of the physical culture system is to prepare a person for a proper life. The tasks of physical education of primary school students are defined taking into account the age-specific characteristics of children, but the general goal of physical culture is not overlooked.

In the physical education of elementary school students, the school provides health care, education and training tasks. Through the national games of the people, there are more opportunities to fulfill these tasks as a whole.

1. Rehabilitation tasks. The main task of physical education of 7-8-year-old elementary school students is to protect the child's life and strengthen his health, to protect himself by exercising his body and to increase resistance to various diseases, external is to teach to cope with adverse environmental conditions.

It is also necessary to make it possible to improve the activity of the cardiovascular system: to increase the flow of blood to the heart, to improve the normal functioning of the heart and to develop its ability to adapt to an unexpectedly changed load; increase the mobility of the chest, ensure deep breathing and long-term stability of this activity, increase the vital capacity of the lungs, improve breathing through the nose, correct internal organs ensuring the functioning of the brain, improving the central nervous system; it is necessary to ensure that the mobility of the states of excitement and inhibition is at the same level, as well as to perfect the motor analyzer and sensory organs.

2. Teaching duties. It is also important to perform educational tasks in the process of conducting national folk games with 7-8 year old students. These tasks are: formation of movement skills and abilities, development of physical qualities (agility, speed, endurance, balance, dexterity, strength, endurance), proper body posture, assimilation of knowledge about physical education. Due to the flexibility of the nervous system, movement skills are formed in children more easily than in adults. Movement skills facilitate the child's communication with the environment and help him perceive it.

Knowledge directly related to physical education for primary school students (useful side of games, importance and technical performance of

physical training, methods of their performance, rules of national games, etc.) providing information is of great importance. The deeper the knowledge that students have, the more intelligently they can use folk games, the more effectively they can engage in games, and the more they can independently use physical culture tools in the school and family environment.

3. Educational tasks. Engaging in physical culture in the body, instilling in children the habit of following the established order, and, if possible, the desire to regularly engage in folk games every day, and to teach them this game at school and at home. It is necessary to develop the ability to independently deal with children, to organize games in groups of children of their age group and younger than them, to teach them to play them together. It is necessary to educate students to look at national games with love, with interest in the results of these games, and with envy at the victories achieved by athletes.

In 2017, the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the subject of physical education in the State Education Standard and the curriculum of general education schools. - 66 hours for classes, 68 hours for classes 2-3-4, as well as training of sports such as gymnastics, athletics, action games, elements of sports games: basketball, volleyball, handball, football, chess

According to the content and organization of the physical education lesson, it has its own characteristics and is held in a sports hall, special facilities, playgrounds, school yard, stadium corridors, special conditions are created for students in such places. Pupils are required to wear special sports clothes instead of regular school uniforms in physical education classes. It will be convenient to perform physical activities.

In general, there is a need for regular reform and improvement of the process of educating students through sports. Therefore, it is appropriate to conduct regular research on this issue, direct experts and scientists to scientific research, and make effective use of the results. Each social system, each society has educational, spiritual, educational and scientific-religious norms, criteria and principles of development aimed at the formation of physical culture, and it originates from the nature of the pedagogical process in the educational system. is organized without After all, raising a physically healthy generation is a need of state importance, and through this, it is aimed at improving the genetic quality of the nations and peoples living in the country and preparing the ground for the birth of healthy generations in the future. As a result of today's global environmental problems and changes in nature, increasing levels of weather and

water pollution and a shortage of clean water, a decrease in soil fertility, and the negative consequences of industrialization, the level of health of society and the culture of a healthy lifestyle are going backwards day by day. The large number of deaths during childbirth, the negative consequences of water and air poisoning, and the deterioration of nature and atmosphere in general have a negative impact on human health. "In order to preserve the nation's gene pool at the population and individual level, it is becoming important for society members to follow a healthy lifestyle. Based on them, special attention is paid to the development of valeological competence, which determines the healthy health, physical and intellectual development of the subjects of education who will take up the specialty profession in the future".[2] In such a situation, it is possible to save the future of humanity by changing the physical culture and attitude to a healthy lifestyle in society.

In fact, the role of sports in educating students through sports is incomparable. It is effective to conduct sports training by connecting it with education and pedagogical process. That is why research is being carried out today in foreign scientific research centers to develop the methodology and technology of forming physical culture in students, and to improve its efficiency. Also, "physical training and sports are used as a spiritual and ideological tool in the formation of the national gene pool, the proper organization of a healthy lifestyle, and the healthy upbringing of the young generation. Today, we are trying to build a democratic society based on the heritage of our ancestors, national values, and based on the requirements of our own lifestyle. The basis of these actions is the healthy human factor. Forming a healthy person through physical education and sports should be the task of the whole society".[3] Today, the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, brought the preparation and orientation of young people to the process of mass sports rehabilitation at the level of state policy. According to the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "deciding on a healthy lifestyle is a vitally important issue for us" [4]. Therefore, within the framework of the reforms being carried out in our country, it is the demand of the time to increase the scope of practical work aimed at forming a physical and healthy lifestyle culture among students. After all, "a healthy lifestyle is a social phenomenon that provides life activities based on the acquisition of skills that serve to ensure the safety of a person's life and health, as well as ensuring the achievement of a high level of health" .[5] Therefore, it is possible to build a healthy society by creating a healthy social environment, and for this, it is one of the priority tasks to direct young people to the process of

public sports health from the school age. Also, within the framework of work on "educating young people in the spirit of spiritual maturity and becoming physically healthy individuals, covering them with useful activities, and ensuring protection from ideological threats, citizens' self-government development and implementation of effective mechanisms of cooperation of sports organizations with sports organizations"[6] also helps to increase the attitude to a healthy lifestyle in the society, attention to health care.

Based on the above opinions, the theoretical-methodological content and social necessity of the formation of physical culture in students consists of the following:

- In-depth study and analysis of the process of ensuring the integration of physical and spiritual-ethical education in the formation of physical culture in students as a pedagogical problem;
- development of principles and laws specific to the educational system regarding the formation of physical culture in students;
- creation of scientific-pedagogical criteria for physical fitness, physical maturity, physical development, physical health strengthening and healthy lifestyle through physical education.

The most important primary rules representing the laws of education and training are called the principles of training. In the process of physical education, general pedagogical principles can be applied, because this process is a special phenomenon of education and training. Reflecting its characteristics in the field of physical education, it is of special importance.

The principle of systematicity and consistency solves the problems of learning physical exercises and movements in the same system in a form that develops from simple to complex. The requirements of the physical education program are constantly being studied. New learning materials are connected and reinforced with physical exercises learned. Based on the program, if simple exercises are learned first, the technique and tactics of complex exercises are gradually formed. When teaching exercises at different levels, exercises are developed from simple to complex. At the same time, they are changed during each training session.

The principle of strengthening knowledge and competence and skills requires constant repetition, strengthening and development of educational materials. Because, if the skills and skills of performing physical movements are not repeated, the skills and skills of the exercise will be lost. Therefore, when planning educational materials, it is necessary to correctly distribute exercises

and reflect their execution from simple to complex. Learned physical exercises. their independent performance in regular classes will strengthen and improve their skills and abilities.

The principle of consciousness and activity: the level of learning exercises in the process of physical education depends on the consciousness and activity of students. Therefore, the principle of awareness and activity is widely used during training. Students' understanding of educational materials is realized through the principle of consciousness, assimilation of them and conscious perception and execution of exercises, as well as improvement of the achieved results.

Exercise is voluntary action controlled by the mind. In the formation of movement skills, the performance of movements is raised to the level of automation. It cannot be said that there is no conscious movement, because one consciously learns physical exercises in order to bring the movement to the level of automation. Teachers and trainers monitor, evaluate and correct the mistakes of the participants. Nevertheless, it is important to develop the ability of the participants to evaluate and control their own actions. In this, the methods of pre-sensing and testing actions are often used.

The principle of directiveness. In pedagogic experience, instructiveness is understood as the implementation of educational tasks by influencing the feelings of sight, hearing and perception of students. Instruction plays an important role in the process of physical education, because the activity of the student is mainly practical and has one of its special tasks, which is the comprehensive development of the senses. In the process of physical education, direct instruction consists in demonstrating physical exercises, as well as "feeling" these exercises in personal experience. Direct instruction can include physical exercises and demonstrations by actually performing activities. Indirect instruction includes, firstly, the use of pictures, schemes, models, cinemagrams, video films and other instructional tools, as well as various special technical means that show certain aspects of actions and facilitate their direct perception, and secondly, figurative language. enters.

The principle of performance In physical education, students are taught a series of more complex physical exercises after the formation of learned physical exercise techniques and skills. Easy exercises reduce student activity. Therefore, it is necessary to give them physical exercises according to their physical level and improve them. Students' body adapts to the same form of exercise. Increasing the amount, size, and shape of exercises ensures the physical

development of children's bodies. Otherwise, the body of students will adapt to the same physical exercises, and their body will not develop physically.

The principle of performance and individualization means taking into account the characteristics of the students and how difficult or easy the task is given to them. It means that the process of education and upbringing in physical education should be organized taking into account the capabilities of the participants, age and gender characteristics, level of preparation, as well as individual differences in physical and spiritual abilities.

The principle of regularity is manifested in the regularity of physical education and sports training, as well as the regularity of alternating rest with physical exertion. The benefits of regular exercise are immeasurable. The regularity of the physical education process is mainly a feature of how much it depends on the most convenient sequence of loading and rest. Continuity - physical education is a continuous process from all periods of human life.

The functional and structural changes occurring in the body due to physical exercise come into conflict, the conditioned reflex connection begins to fade, the achieved level of functional capabilities decreases, and even some regressive changes 5 - It becomes known even after 7 days of no training.

The principle of development. This principle expresses the general direction of the demands placed on those engaged in the process of physical education and involves setting and performing new and increasingly difficult tasks, and gradually increasing the volume and intensity of related loads. contains z. Physical education is also in constant movement and growth, with continuous changes from training to training, from stage to stage. In this case, increasing the complexity of the exercises and decreasing the effectiveness is a characteristic sign.

In the process of physical education, along with the complexity of the form of movement activity, all components of physical load should also increase. This power is seen in the laws of improving physical qualities such as speed and endurance. It has been determined that the level of positive changes in the body under the influence of physical exercises is proportional to the volume and intensity of the load. If it is observed that the physical load does not lead to exhaustion, the greater the volume of the load, the more important and stronger the adaptation process will be; the more intense the load, the better the recovery and "ultra-recovery" processes.

The method of individual approach to students in physical education classes is also widely used in the organization of classes in medical groups of students.

Teachers arrange for sick students to engage in permitted physical exercises according to the level of their illness. It also defines measures for physical development of physically weak students. When conducting physical education activities in such a group, the teacher should limit the amount of exercises, the number of repetitions, ease the conditions of performance, engage in special exercises, and pay attention to the indicators of the exercises. Teachers should be in constant cooperation with doctors when training in medical groups. In the individual approach to children, it is necessary to take into account their health, age, gender, physical fitness and physical abilities.

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